

**CONCEPT AND DEVELOPMENT OF TAX MONITORING IN
UZBEKISTAN**

Azizov Abrorjon Salidjanovich

Commercial Director of Inter Food LLC

salma.aa@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11124532>

Since the beginning of the 90s, the formation of a tax system in Uzbekistan has been taking place in new economic conditions. It should be noted that the first stage of the formation of the tax system was characterized by massive tax evasion. This state of affairs at that time, in our opinion, can be explained by the lack of developed legal institutions, the low level of tax discipline and weak state tax control.

The actively pursued tax reform of recent years, which consists of unifying tax legislation, as well as strengthening the system of tax control by the state, in our opinion, was able to reverse this negative trend.

At the same time, the success of creating an effective tax system depends on further improvement of the mechanisms for managing tax relations, which includes tax regulation and tax administration.

It is worth noting that in the scientific literature there is still a debate about the essence and relationship of the above-mentioned concepts. Adhering to the point of view of scientists who believe that tax administration is the activity of tax authorities to monitor compliance with tax legislation, we believe that the concepts of “tax regulation” and “tax administration” require separation from each other.

Joining the point of view of a number of scientists, we believe that tax regulation is a set of measures of indirect influence of the state on the economy, involving the creation and improvement of tax legislation through the introduction, collection and abolition of taxes, the definition of subjects and objects of taxation, the procedure for forming the tax base, as well as the use tax rates and benefits.

The dynamic nature of the development of tax relations, in our opinion, requires further improvement, since in the context of the globalization of the world economy, leading to the free flow of financial, labor and material resources, there is a need to ensure the competitiveness of the Uzbek tax system against the background of the tax systems of other countries. In our opinion, the ability of the country’s economy to attract foreign investment, develop

individual sectors of the economy, and ensure an innovative path for the development of the state depends on how well the tax system is “tuned.”

In connection with the need to improve tax regulation and increase the efficiency of tax administration in the context of constantly changing economic processes, we consider it necessary to create in Uzbekistan a specialized system for continuous monitoring, assessment and forecasting of changes in the state of the state tax system. We believe that to define this system, we can use the term “tax monitoring”, which, firstly, should act as a kind of “barometer” of the competitiveness of the state tax system, and secondly, contribute to the high-quality selection of objects of control and areas of control activities carried out by tax authorities .

It should be noted that certain areas of tax monitoring are already successfully implemented in the practice of tax authorities, in particular, when selecting taxpayers as part of planning on-site tax audits. However, to date, scientific research related to a systematic theoretical study of tax monitoring as a mechanism for managing the tax system does not exist, and certain elements of its implementation in the practical activities of tax authorities require further improvement.

It should be noted that in the Uzbek and foreign financial and economic literature there is no definition of the term “tax monitoring”, while the concept is used in the practical activities of tax authorities mainly in connection with the implementation of pre-audit analysis of taxpayers, an example of which is the creation of the Concept for planning on-site tax audits. In foreign literature, the term “monitoring of tax discipline” is used.

By highlighting tax monitoring as an economic category, we have defined its functions and principles. The functions of tax monitoring, in our opinion, should include: information, analytical, managerial, control. Among the principles of tax monitoring are: continuity, timeliness, complexity.

The content of tax monitoring, in our opinion, is most clearly manifested in comparison with such economic categories as state tax management, tax control, pre-audit analysis of taxpayers, financial analysis, based on key system-forming features: essence, purpose, subject, object, subject and task .

Tax monitoring, in our opinion, is one of the tools of state tax management, while the object of management is the state tax system. We believe that tax monitoring has independent significance, firstly, from the point of view of tax regulation, and secondly, from the point of view of tax administration.

Practice shows that the existence of tax risks of the state is associated with the presence of gaps in legislation, and also depends on the effectiveness of the tax administration system created in the state: is it capable of ensuring the completeness and timeliness of taxpayers fulfilling their obligations based on real, rather than declared, indicators of financial and economic activity .

In this regard, the tax authorities need to create a specialized system for identifying “problem” taxpayers in order to apply tax control sanctions to them. This reveals the need for tax monitoring from the point of view of tax administration, while the main direction of tax monitoring is the continuous monitoring of the financial condition of taxpayers.

Article 169 of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan the subject of tax monitoring is compliance with tax legislation, correctness of calculation, completeness and timeliness of payment (transfer) of taxes and fees by a legal entity in respect of which tax monitoring is carried out.

Therefore, our research allowed us to formulate the following definition of tax monitoring as an economic category. Tax monitoring is a set of forms and methods for managing tax relations, based on constant monitoring, assessment and forecasting of changes in the state of the state tax system.

References:

1. Kozimbek Goziev. Principles of tax legislation. International Scientific and Current Research Conferences. 2021. P.9-12.
2. I Turaboev, M Berdikulov. Tax monitoring as a new form of tax control. Review of law sciences. V.2. 2018 P.18.

